

Corporate Social Responsibility in India: Concerns and Difficulties

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Abstract:

It's true that "It's simple to evade our obligations, but we can't dodge the consequences." Josiah Charles Stamp, 1880-1941, Bank of England director. Businesses must be conscious of what and how they do things in this digitalized environment. The company's brand depends on its influence on society, the environment, and the economy, not just product quality. Social responsibility gives them an edge in a congested market. CSR integrates commercial and social goals. The company prioritizes People, Earth, and Profit while meeting stakeholder expectations. Equal opportunity, poverty reduction, basic rights, and robust human development motivate most policy measures in the country. Our choices now will impact future generations. Inequality persists. This year, India introduced new CSR standards. Indian enterprises must spend 2% of net earnings on CSR under these standards. India was the first to mandate CSR. The CSR obligation under Companies Act, 2013 is an excellent way to involve the corporate sector in fair development. Companies have to spend 2% of profits on CSR and justify their failure to do so. Nevertheless, the current amendment requires corporations to spend 2% of revenues on CSR within a certain timeframe or donate this amount to government-run entities. The proposed amendment will force CSR-qualified enterprises to spend the stipulated portion of their income on CSR without fail. This article examines CSR issues in India and the variables that drive CSR efforts in Indian companies.

Keywords: Legal Obligations, Triple Bottom Line, Sustainable Development, Social Responsibility, Voluntary Desire.

Introduction:

Although the notion of corporate social responsibility (CSR) is not new, it is unquestionably the newest buzzword in the business world. Throughout the past few decades, its popularity has grown. In India, corporate giving is nothing new. CSR, however, goes beyond simple altruism and giving. CSR is a method of conducting business through which corporate entities offer value and support social good. It may be characterized as a sense of obligation on the part of the businesses to the society and environment in which they operate. An umbrella term for a variety of theories and practices that all acknowledge the following: (a) that businesses have a responsibility for their impact on society and the environment, sometimes beyond legal compliance and individual liability; (b) that businesses have a responsibility for the behavior of others with whom they do business (for example, within supply chains); and (c) that businesses need to manage their relationship with wider society, whether for reasons of business or for social good. Bloweld and Fryna. Businesses can fulfil this obligation by implementing a variety of policies and starting new initiatives that will benefit society as a whole. Companies that practice corporate social responsibility work to balance their economic, social, and environmental

goals. Taking on CSR projects may provide businesses a competitive edge and aid in brand development. Laborers (people), capital, and technology are necessary for operating a business, but morality is also important for maintaining the entities' unity. Making "sustainability" a way of thinking and doing is crucial for the business. Businesses must make an effort to add value to the world as well as to its clients, customers, or other stakeholders. The idea of corporate social responsibility has several facets. It has four interconnected elements, including the economic, legal, ethical, and altruistic ones. The economic, legal, ethical, and charitable obligations that society currently has of corporations are included in what is known as "corporate social responsibility." — Carroll.

Various Dimensions and Obligations:

Economic Dimension: This dimension pertains to a firm's duty to the company, such as ensuring a reasonable amount of returns to investors, proper pay for workers, offering goods to customers at reasonable pricing, responding to business risks appropriately, etc. The first and most significant factor is the economic dimension. It acts as the base or starting point for other dimensions. **Legal Dimension:** In order for a firm to be considered socially responsible, it must follow by all applicable laws and game rules. Laws are directives and rules that outline what is

acceptable and unacceptable behavior. Every business must abide by these dos and don'ts codifications in order to thrive over the long term. The ethical component is a representation of what society expects from business entities. The public expects the business to go above and beyond the call of duty to better serve them. It is what the public expects of the corporations in addition to their fiscal and legal obligations. The philanthropic dimension embodies the firms' selfless desire to help their workers, neighbours, or society at large. The general public wants this. It is entirely up to the business whether or not to assist charitable organizations, educational institutions, the environment, or other causes.

Just a few academics specifically mentioned the three elements of stakeholders, voluntarism, and environment. The obligation of the business towards its stakeholders, such as its shareholders, workers, customers, clients, suppliers, and the government, is covered by the stakeholder dimension. Businesses must be aware of their obligations to them and make an effort to match their objectives with those of the company. The voluntary desire of the business to improve society as a whole and make it a better place to live is reflected in the voluntariness factor. The company's obligation to the ecology is the primary emphasis of the environmental dimension. Companies need to make an effort to combine environmental and financial objectives. To preserve our environment and promote sustainability, green actions must be implemented.

CSR activities have the potential to be very advantageous for both the business and society. The CSR initiatives serve a wide range of stakeholders that are connected to business entities. Companies now give back to society and aid in nation-building as a result of growing knowledge of several modern concerns impacting society and the environment (Grant Thornton IBR, 2014). Some of the elements that influence CSR in India are:

The cost management is essential for businesses to thrive in this cutthroat economy. Businesses that operate on a tight budget are seen as sustainable and responsible. For instance, the cost to the nation of gases like carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases is enormous. A business finds a means to control the emission of these harmful gases while also benefiting the environment. This driver is crucial for assessing the success of the business and its level of social responsiveness.

1. Tax Relief: Another significant factor influencing CSR is the benefits of CSR, such as tax advantages. Business entities that engage in CSR are granted tax breaks by the government in

exchange for their charitable activities and ecological preservation. Relief from taxes is very beneficial to developing nations like India. In order to claim tax benefits, it is crucial for businesses to maintain openness in their CSR initiatives.

2. Consumer Demand: People patronize businesses that engage in CSR. Companies are motivated to contribute to society and sustainability efforts by customer demands for them to be socially and environmentally responsible. By making the ethical choice to purchase a product made by a business that participates in CSR, consumers support CSR initiatives.
3. Value Shift: The business entities have experienced a value change. As they have begun to focus on ethics, they believe that doing good for society is the correct thing to do. They currently hold the view that economic growth goals may be combined with social and environmental goals. They strive to improve communities and the lives of its residents because of their values.
4. Brand Building: Businesses think that engaging in CSR strengthens their image in the marketplace and builds their brand. Customers and clients are very appreciative of businesses' efforts on behalf of society, and this fact encourages businesses to do their part for the common good. They gain a better reputation in the international market as a result.

Purpose of the Study:

The goals of the current paper are to: i. review the literature on various aspects of CSR; ii. discuss the CSR provisions in India; iii. study the acceptance and implementation of CSR by Indian companies; iv. analyze various issues and challenges associated with CSR; and v. suggest some measures to ensure improved CSR practices in India.

It should be noted that the secondary data serves as the sole foundation for this investigation. To make the necessary inferences, a thorough study of the literature was conducted systematically. Journals, newspaper articles, textbooks, e-books, corporate reports, search engines, company websites, scholarly articles, research papers, and other academic publications were some of the secondary sources of data utilized.

A review of the works

Rahman (2011) examined many CSR facets. To determine CSR dimensions, a number of CSR definitions from the 1950s to the present were examined. In the 1950s, CSR was seen as a duty to society, and in the 1960s, it was seen as a partnership between corporate entities and society. Throughout the

1970s to 1990s, additional elements like as stakeholders, ethics, voluntarism, philanthropy, environmental stewardship, and the triple bottom line were incorporated in CSR definitions. The CSR dimensions of the twenty-first century cover a considerably larger range of topics, such as increasing citizen quality of life, human and labour rights, environmental difficulties, corruption problems, and challenges with transparency and accountability, in addition to the previously mentioned components.

In today's contemporary and globalized world, CSR is an unavoidable concern for business entities, according to Majumdar et al. (2008). They looked at current CSR approaches and sought to identify challenges they might face in practice in poor nations. Several approaches based on the institutional approach and the academic approach were considered. They proposed that in order to close the gap between developed and poor nations, a conceptual framework for corporate social responsibility is essential. In engaging in CSR, all five domains—economic, ethical, legal, philanthropic, and environmental—must be taken into consideration.

In their 2016 study, Prieto-Carrón et al. sought to update the CSR study with fresh perspectives. They discussed the results of CSR projects, the connection between business and poverty, problems with power & participation in CSR, and aspects of CSR that have to do with governance. According to them, just one aspect of CSR is now being investigated and evaluated, and a number of delicate issues surrounding it are disregarded. The need to carefully weigh the benefits and drawbacks of CSR programmes in developing nations is urgent. They recommended conducting joint studies on CSR by scholars and CSR practitioners in order to improve effect evaluation approaches. Any significant concerns that have been neglected or not handled must receive attention.

Legal Provisions for CSR in India:

The CSR is covered under Schedule VII of the Companies Act of 2013 and Section 135 (Corporate Social Responsibility) Regulations, 2014, respectively. Every business, including its holding and subsidiary firms, is expected to abide by all CSR regulations if it has a net worth of at least Rs. 500 crore, an annual revenue of at least Rs. 1000 crore, and a net profit of at least Rs. 5 crore. Any business that qualifies for CSR must establish a board-level CSR committee. The firm's board of directors must make sure that, in accordance with its CSR policy, the specific company spends at least 2% of the average net income from the three most recent fiscal years in each fiscal year. Formerly, businesses had to conform or provide justifications for not complying, and they

could then get away with it. But, escaping will not be as simple now that Section 135 of the Companies Act, 2013, has undergone a fresh revision (2019). The section was amended to include a clause stating that if a corporation is unable to use the target amount set aside for CSR operations, it must transfer the money to one of the funds listed in schedule VII, such as the Prime Minister's National Relief Fund. The remaining funds must be transferred to the designated fund within 30 days of the third financial year's end date. Every business that violates Section 135's rules must pay a fine between Rs. 50,000 and Rs. 25, 000 if found guilty. Moreover, cops may face up to three years in prison under the regulations. All business enterprises that meet the SR requirements are required by the act's criminal clause to engage in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), and it outlines the fines and jail time for doing so.

The following causes may benefit from the firms' contributions:

1. The eradication of poverty, malnutrition, and hunger.
2. Promotion of sanitation and health.
3. Supporting employment and education that can improve vocational skills.
4. Promoting gender parity.
5. Ensuring sustainability.
6. Preserving culture, art, and history
7. Contributing to the military of the nation.
8. Promoting and instructing sporting activities.
9. Making a donation to the humanitarian effort.

Challenges and Problems:

An operating a business while considering your social responsibilities is a difficult challenge. Today's businesses need to think about more than simply earnings if they want to satisfy their stakeholders. They are still learning how to preserve harmony between the company's strategic goals and social and environmental considerations. The following are a few of the difficulties the business may encounter when implementing CSR:

Failing to Have a Holistic Perspective of CSR:

Businesses continue to see CSR in a limited way. They are unable to grasp the holistic perspective of CSR, which holds that CSR affects nearly all of the company's stakeholders as well as society and the environment as a whole. Seeing new opportunities and using them to address societal issues is crucial for businesses. They need to combine corporate goals with ecological and social goals in an effort to produce shared value. The company should integrate CSR into all aspects of its operations and should be very clear on where it should focus its investments.

Lack of Transparency: Transparency is a crucial need for the success and effective execution of CSR strategy inside a firm. Transparency and CSR go hand in hand. This enables diverse firm stakeholders to have a thorough understanding of numerous topics that are important to them. Window-dressing is a technique used in organizations to disguise information from stakeholders. Today's society requires CSR, thus they also require CSR transparency. The current state of corporate openness is utterly inadequate. Businesses don't put enough effort into disclosing pertinent information. Something comes between the development of community and business trust. Lack of transparency is the main obstacle CSR faces since it is essential for the success of any CSR programme. Aligning the Company's Development Objectives with the Interests of its Shareholders It is a significant problem and extremely vital to balance social responsibility with economic performance. A significant obstacle in the way of CSR is the production of shared and sustainable value, which integrates the company's development objectives with the interests of its stakeholders.

Greenwashing:

India has a high level of inequality. The CSR law lacks a forceful enforcement mechanism and does not go far enough in addressing inequality. Because CSR is not sufficiently clear, it creates the appearance of advancement. This results in widespread greenwashing. One of the main obstacles to CSR effectiveness and compliance is this.

Inadequate Financial Resources:

Local Capabilities, and Infrastructure: CSR may need significant expenditures. As a result, businesses need to carefully plan and priorities their investments. Prior to implementing initiatives, careful planning of the resources to be used and the problems to be solved is required. Moreover, there is a dearth of appropriate infrastructure and local capacity. As there are no reliable governmental or non-governmental institutions that can support CSR, it is imperative to develop local capabilities and infrastructure facilities for CSR implementation that is successful.

Lack of Consensus:

Businesses' CSR programmes are duplicated as a result of the lack of consensus among various local agencies and business organizations. This encourages unneeded competition among businesses, which works against the primary goal of creating value for society.

Lack of Community Participation:

Communities for which CSR is to be done tend to be less interested in the activities and programmes planned by corporations. Moreover,

inadequate attempts are made to promote CSR initiatives within communities, which results in a lack of confidence among the populace. One of the main issues with CSR is the lack of communication between businesses and communities.

Conclusion and Suggestions:

Increasing public awareness of corporate social responsibility is one challenge to be overcome. Creating a long-term objective and sustainable perspective on CSR activities is necessary to close the gap between all the key stakeholders and implement CSR operations successfully.

To address a variety of difficulties, businesses must develop CSR procedures. To prevent duplication of effort, they should take the development agenda into much greater consideration.

the pooling of resources and creation of synergies between businesses and non-governmental groups to undertake CSR operations more successfully and efficiently.

It is important to make efforts for the underprivileged and needy in both urban and rural locations.

Corporate houses that are contributing to the needs and well-being of the underprivileged should receive honours and rewards from the government. making CSR a required course or discipline in schools, colleges, or universities to sensitize pupils. This strategy will inspire the next generation and prepare them for challenges to come. Also, to offer more creative ideas for the general improvement of society and the environment.

Reported Sustainability: The increased awareness of sustainability-related concerns has led to an increase in the importance of sustainability reporting. The Global Reporting Initiative is a group that offers a framework for sustainable reporting (GRI). The GRI's sustainability reporting guidelines are often employed by corporate entities. A sustainability report accurately portrays the company's sustainability performance. It encompasses both an organization's beneficial and detrimental contributions to sustainability. It provides all relevant information on the objectives, plans, commitments, and methods adopted by the company.

References:

1. Dhawan, S. (2019) 'Green HR Practices and Environment Sustainability: A Study of Indian Companies', *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, Vol. 6, No. 4, pp. 501-508.
2. Dubbink, W., Graafland, J.J. and Liedekerke, LV. (2008) 'CSR, Transparency and the Role of Intermediate Organizations', *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 82, No. 2, pp. 391-406.

3. Du, S. and Bhattacharya, CB., (2010) 'Maximizing Business Returns to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): The Role of CSR Communication', *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 12, No. 1, pp. 56.
4. Handbook on Corporate Social Responsibility in India: PWC-CII
5. <https://www.pwc.in/assets/pdfs/publications/2013/handbook-on-corporate-social-responsibility-in-india.pdf>
6. Jothi, M. (2016) 'Driving Factors of Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in India: An Empirical Study Based on the Perceptions of Selected Executives from Public and Private Firms in India', *Amity Journal of Corporate Governance*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 39- 53.
7. Majumdar, M. and Nazmul, A., (2008) 'Challenges of the Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in Developing Countries', Department of Management, Faculty of Business and Economics, Monash University, Australia.
8. Nicolae, J.C. and Sabina, J.M. (2010) 'Dimensions and Challenges of Social Responsibility', *Annales Universitatis Apulensis Series Oeconomica*, Vol. 12, No. 1, pp. 238-247.
9. Rajput, N., Batra, G. and Pathak, R. (2012) 'Linking CSR and Financial Performance: An Empirical Validation', *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, Vol. 10, No. 2, pp. 56.
10. Prathima, D.S. (2015): The 10 Companies with Best CSR Reputations. Proceedings of the Second European Academic Research Conference on Global Business, Economics, Finance and Banking (EAR15 Swiss Conference), Paper ID: Z5100.
11. Prieto-Carron, M., Lund-Thomsen, P., Chan, A., Muro, A. and Bhushan, C. (2006) 'Critical Perspectives on CSR and Development: What We Know, What We Don't Know, and What We Need to Know', *International Affairs*, Vol. 82, No. 5, pp. 977-987.
12. Rahman, S. (2011) 'Evaluation of Definitions: Ten Dimensions of Corporate Social Responsibility', *World Review of Business Research*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 166-176.
13. Sharma, E. and Mani, M. (2013) 'Corporate Social Responsibility: An Analysis of Indian Commercial Banks', *AIMA Journal of Management & Research*, Vol. 7, No. 4, pp. 56-62.